

XXXII International Astronomical Union,
General Assembly, Cape Town, SA,
6-15 August, 2024

POST MEETING REPORT

Focus Meeting 9: Measures of Luminous and Dark Matter in Galaxies Across Time

Meeting Website: <https://ga24dmfm9.sao.ac.za/>

Coordinating Divisions: Division-J “Galaxies and Cosmology”,

Supporting working Groups: Working Group of Junior Members,
Women in Astronomy Working Group,

Location: Cape Town, South Africa

Dates of Meeting: 13th and 15th August 2024

Number of Participants: 105

Total IAU Grant received: 13,745 euros (given to 23 participants)

Total African Grant received: 8093 euros (given to 11 participants)

Scientific Organizing Committee & Chairs:

(w: woman / m: man - junior: j / senior: s /)

Name	Institution	Country	Gender	IAU Member
Gauri Sharma	University of Western Cape	South Africa	F	Junior
Sabine Thater	University of Vienna	Austria	F	Junior
Jonathan Freundlich	Observatoire Astronomique de Strasbourg	France	M	Junior
Mousumi Das	Indian Institute of Astrophysics	India	F	Senior
Benoit Famaey,	Observatoire Astronomique de Strasbourg	France	M	Senior
Marie Korsaga	University Joseph Ki-Zerbo	Burkina Faso	F	Junior
Julien Laval	Lab. Univers et Particules de Montpellier	France	M	Senior
Chung Pei Ma,	University of California,	Berkeley, United States	F	Senior
Moses Mogotsi	South African Astronomical Observatory	South Africa	M	Junior
Cristina C. Popescu	University of Central Lancashire	United Kingdom	F	Senior
Francesca Rizzo,	Cosmic Dawn Centre,	Denmark	F	Junior
Laura Sales,	University of California, Riverside	United States	F	Senior
Miguel A. Sánchez-Conde,	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Spain	M	Senior
Glenn van de Ven	University of Vienna	Austria	M	Senior
HongSheng Zhao	University of St. Andrews	United Kingdom	M	Senior
Alice Zocchi	University of Vienna	Austria	F	Junior

women:9/16, men:7/16, junior member:7/16, and senior member:8/16

SOC were chosen from all four major continents, with no more than 30% from any one specific country. Gender and age was balanced, with priority given to young researchers and women.

Scientific Program:

Tuesday 13 August

Session 1: Observational constraints on dark matter			Chair: Gauri Sharma	Status
10:30 - 10:55	Sedona Price	Observational constraints on dark matter in galaxies over the last 10 billion years	in-person	Invited
10:55 - 11:10	Caroline Foster	The dynamical and morphological transformation of galaxies through cosmic time	in-person	Contributed
11:10 - 11:25	Lai Yee Lilian Lee	The CRISTAL survey: Resolving kinematics of typical main-sequence star-forming galaxies at $4 < z < 6$	in-person	Contributed
11:25 - 11:40	Teymoor Saifollahi	Weighing dark matter in dwarf galaxies in the Perseus galaxy cluster	in-person	Contributed
11:40 - 11:55	Luísa Buzzo	A comprehensive view of the luminous and dark matter content of ultra-diffuse galaxies	in-person	Contributed
11:55 - 11:58	E. d.T.	Dark matter halos and scaling relations of extremely massive spiral galaxies	in-person	Flash Talk
11:58 - 12:01	Michael Fall	Dynamical evidence that galaxies of different morphologies occupy dark matter halos of different masses	in-person	Flash Talk

Session 2: Observational constraints on dark matter			Chair: Jonathan Freundlich	Status
13:30-13:55	Kyle Oman	The many ways that dwarf galaxy rotation curves can fail as mass tracers	in-person	Invited
13:55 - 14:10	Catherine Cerny	Probing Inner Dark Matter Density Profiles with MUSE Kinematics and Strong Lensing	in-person	Contributed
14:10 - 14:25	Carlos Carneiro	Joint modelling of strong gravitational lensing and stellar dynamics.	in-person	Contributed
14:25 - 14:40	Jessica Doppel	Imposters among us: globular cluster kinematics and the halo mass of ultra-diffuse galaxies in clusters	in-person	Contributed
14:40 - 14:43	Surhud More	Linking galaxies with dark matter halos using weak gravitational lensing	online	Flash Talk
14:43 - 14:46	Suchira Sarkar	Massive disc galaxies with high surface brightness plus low surface brightness stellar disks, hosted by massive dark matter halo - a TNG50 simulation study	online	Flash Talk
14:46 - 14:49	Richard McDermid	The evolution of total mass density slopes, dark matter content, and orbital structure since $z=0.3$ from resolved integral field stellar kinematics from MAGPI	in-person	Flash Talk
14:49 - 14:52	Nathan Deg	The Kinematic Scaling Relations of the WALLABY Pilot Galaxies	in-person	Flash Talk
14:52 - 14:55	Famenontsoa Rakotondrainy	Comparative analysis of dark matter distribution in HI-rich galaxies	in-person	Flash Talk

Session 3: LCDM challenges and simulations			Chair: Sedona Price	Status
15:30 - 15:55	Federico Lelli	The dynamical scaling laws of rotation-supported galaxies	in-person	Invited
15:55 - 16:10	Pavel Mancera Piña	An ultra-deep and ultra-sharp view on gas-rich ultra-diffuse galaxies: a population defying CDM	in-person	Contributed
16:10 - 16:25	Zahra Basti	Calibrating Mass Modeling Methods with Numerical Simulations of Galaxies	in-person	Contributed
16:25 - 16:40	Nondh Panithanpaisal	Populations of Subhalos Beyond the Virial Radius: Splashback vs. Field Subhalos in FIRE	in-person	Contributed

16:40 - 16:55	Michael Fall (p.p. Aaron Ludlow)	The impact of spurious collisional heating on the spatial distribution and kinematics of stellar and dark matter particles in simulated galaxies	in-person	Contributed
16:55 - 16:58	Ji Hoon Kim	The Formation of Late-type Galaxies: Nature versus Nurture	in-person	Flash Talk
16:58 - 17:01	Nikhil Arora	Quantifying the inner halo response to active galactic nuclei feedback in galaxies	in-person	Flash Talk

Thursday 15 August

Session 4: Constraining dark matter particle candidates			Chair: Federico Lelli	Status
10:30 - 10:55	Viviana Gammaldi	Invited talk: Dark matter searches in dwarf irregular galaxies with gamma-ray observatories.	online	Invited
10:55 - 11:10	Carlo Nipoti	Dwarf spheroidal galaxies as dark-matter laboratories	in-person	Contributed
11:10 - 11:25	Nency Patel	Probing Dark Matter with Strong and Weak Gravitational Lensing Mass Models: A Case Study of Abell 2744	in-person	Contributed
11:25 - 11:40	Donggeun Tak	An Indirect search for dark matter with a combined analysis of dwarf spheroidal galaxies from VERITA	in-person	Contributed
11:40 - 11:55	Michael Sarkis	DarkMatters: the complete multi-wavelength WIMP emission simulator	in-person	Contributed
11:55 - 11:58	Samuel Lange	A new Dark Matter detection? Testing lens model complexity in Strong Lensing	in-person	Flash Talk

Session 5: Alternatives to LCDM			Chair: Françoise Combes	Status
13:30 - 13:55	Giulia Despali	Invited talk: Galaxy formation in alternative dark matter scenarios	online	Invited
13:55 - 14:10	Azadeh Fattahi	Galactic halos in alternative dark matter models	in-person	Contributed
14:10 - 14:25	Francesca Fragkoudi	Probing dark matter with bar dynamics	in-person	Contributed
14:25 - 14:40	Przemek Mroz	Constraints on primordial black holes as constituents of dark matter based on over 20 years of OGLE observations of the LargeMagellanicCloud	in-person	Contributed
14:49 - 15:00	Connor Bottrell	From optical imaging to dark matter halo masses with simulation-based inference models	in-person	Contributed
14:40 - 14:43	Surajit Kalita	Fast radio bursts as a probe to constrain primordial mass black holes made of dark matter	in-person	Flash Talk
14:43 - 14:46	Victor Robles	Assessing the effect of supernovae feedback at the centre of dwarf halos of scalar field/fuzzy dark matter	in-person	Flash Talk
14:46 - 14:49	Nilanjana Nandi	Dynamical lineage of HI-rich field ultra-diffuse galaxies	in-person	Flash Talk

Session 6: Perspectives and new techniques			Chair: Caroline Foster	Status
15:30 - 15:55	Francoise Combes	Invited talk: Alternatives to CDM, MOND or Axion-like particles	in-person	Invited
15:55 - 16:10	Florent Renaud	Probing dark matter (or its absence) with galaxy mergers	in-person	Contributed
16:10 - 16:25	John McKean	Testing models for dark matter with extremely high angular resolution imaging of gravitational lenses	in-person	Contributed
16:25 - 16:40	Jiani Chu	Galaxy stellar and total mass estimation using	in-person	Contributed

		machine learning		
16:40 - 16:55	Connor Stone	Caustics: a differentiable, GPU accelerated, gravitational lensing simulator	online	Contributed
16:55 - 16:58	Anupreeta More	Towards statistical constraints on mass distributions of galaxies/groups from strong lens samples	online	Flash Talk

Full Participant List: Attached at the end of this report. This list contains the number of all the participants, submission IDs (UID), full name, talk type, abstract title, age, gender, country of residence, and nationality.

Name and Number of representing countries : South Africa, Australia, Ecuador, Canada, Spain, Madagascar, Russia, Italy, Burkina Faso, France, India, China, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, United Kingdom, United States, Brazil, Chile, Germany, and Mexico. Total 20 countries participated.

Scientific highlights of the meetings:

Recent efforts to measure galaxy dynamical masses and dark matter fractions up to $z \sim 3$, reveals decreasing dark matter fraction within the effective radius with look-back time. Challenges in this analysis include the need for deep data, the galaxy-halo degeneracy, parametrization of mass and kinematic profiles, and corrections for gas pressure support and non-circular motions. Observations from the Atacama Large Millimetre Array (ALMA) CRISTAL survey show that about half of galaxies at $4 < z < 6$ are rotating disks with high velocity dispersions, and low dark matter fractions. Studies of galaxies at $z \sim 0.3$ indicate no environmental dependence on galaxy morphology or rotation. Studies of local galaxies revealed the universality of the HI-to-halo mass ratio in isolated disk galaxies, while dynamics of massive spiral galaxies indicated consistent angular momentum retention. Notably, late-type local galaxies displayed more massive dark matter halos than early-type galaxies at fixed stellar mass. The potential of globular cluster number counts as a mass estimator for dwarf galaxies was discussed, along with insights into the formation of ultra-diffuse galaxies and their dark matter content. Kinematic scaling relations from atomic gas surveys provide insight into future studies with Square Kilometre Array (SKA).

Despite various challenges in gravitational lensing observations, modelling, and analysis, this field has shown an exceptional success in constraining the dark matter content and its distribution. High-resolution imaging via Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) enables testing of various dark matter models, revealing perturbations from dark matter subhalos, with further advancements expected from next-generation arrays like ngVLA and SKA. The integration of stellar velocity dispersion measurements with strong lensing mass models has provided evidence for dark matter cores in brightest cluster galaxies. Additionally, links between stellar mass and dark matter halos indicate a consistent relationship over cosmic time. Discoveries of dark matter substructure candidates using James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) and mass distribution studies of galaxy clusters were also reported. A Graphic Processing Unit- (GPU-) accelerated tool for modelling gravitational lenses that employs Bayesian inference using machine learning was introduced. Machine learning algorithms and a citizen science project have enabled the discovery of hundreds of strong gravitational lenses up to $z \sim 0.8$ in a Hyper Supreme Cam survey. Furthermore, self-consistent modelling combining stellar dynamics and lensing improves measurements of dark matter content in early-type galaxies, despite ongoing challenges in accurately recovering dark matter parameters. Lastly, the gravitational lensing of fast radio bursts presents potential for constraining primordial black hole fractions and modified gravity.

Observations also propose alternatives to conventional (cold) dark matter scenario. The key talks include strong regularities in the distribution of baryons and dark matter across galaxy populations, particularly in rotation-supported galaxies, remarkably flat rotation curves at large radii, the baryonic Tully-Fisher relation linking total baryonic mass with flat rotation velocity, and the central surface density relation connecting baryonic surface density with dynamical mass surface density. These relations are consistent with predictions from modified newtonian dynamics (MOND). Talking about alternatives to cold dark matter, warm dark matter scenarios lead to a reduction in satellite counts and alterations in structure formation, while self-interacting dark matter results in diverse halo density profiles and affects galaxy dynamics. Alternatives such as MOND and fuzzy dark matter present intriguing possibilities; however, a sample of gas-rich ultra-diffuse galaxies deviated from the baryonic Tully-Fisher relation. Dynamical modelling of these galaxies hints low-density and low-concentration halos, which neither match with the predictions of cold dark matter cosmological simulations, nor favours the MOND and fuzzy dark matter; hence, presenting an opportunity to test unexplored nature of dark matter?

The cusp-core problem remains unresolved, with potential solutions including dark matter self-interaction, baryonic processes (e.g., supernova outflows), or modified gravity (e.g., MOND). Uncertainties in kinematic models and observational limitations add complexity to understand the accurate physics even from simulations. NIHAO simulations show that dark matter profiles are well-recovered at large radii, but mismatches of up to 50% occur near galaxy centres due to non-circular motions. FIRE simulations reveal distinct subhalo populations, with splashback subhaloes prone to tidal disruption, which can bias mass estimates. NIHAO simulations also show that AGN feedback reduces central dark matter mass by up to 40%. Furthermore, spurious dynamical heating due to the limited number of particles in simulated galaxies can significantly affect their kinematics and structure. A semi-empirical model has been proposed to identify conditions under which this numerical effect can be neglected in both zoom-in and cosmological simulations.

A few studies particularly focused on stellar distribution in cosmological simulation tend to verify the observations and nature of dark matter. Simulations show that the stellar halos formed in warm dark matter resemble those in cold dark matter due to similar massive accretions, while self-interacting dark matter leads to flatter density profiles and less biased orbits due to shallower gravitational potentials. Bar dynamics were also explored as a means to constrain galaxy formation, suggesting that massive dark matter halos stabilize discs against bar formation.

Recent work on indirect dark matter searches has focused on detecting gamma-ray emissions from dark matter annihilation or decay in regions of high dark matter density, such as dwarf spheroidal and irregular galaxies. Despite extensive searches, including those using ground-based facilities such as VERITAS, MAGIC, MeerKAT array, and HESS Cherenkov telescopes and space observatories (e.g., Fermi-LAT), no clear signals of WIMP or ultra-heavy dark matter have been detected. Central dark matter density estimates in dwarf spheroidal galaxies, combined with J- and D-factors, are key to interpreting γ -ray flux measurements. Further advancements, such as the upcoming Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO), are expected to improve current constraints. Beyond the realm of dark matter particles, primordial black holes also emerge as intriguing candidates for its composition. However, 20 year long gravitational microlensing investigations conducted in the Large Magellanic Cloud have yielded no compelling evidence in their favour.

To conclude, the integration of observations with machine learning, citizen science, and cosmological simulations into dark matter studies is driving compelling research, improving mass estimations, and refining models of galaxy evolution. With upcoming instruments like the Extremely Large Telescope, next-generation Very Large Array, Square Kilometre Array, and the

Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory, future observations are poised to provide further insights, offering a better understanding of dark matter and its role in shaping the galaxies in the Universe. Overall, while significant challenges remain, continued advancements in observational techniques and theoretical models hold the potential to unravel the elusive nature of dark matter and refine our understanding of galaxy formation and evolution.

Science Accessible to public: GA24 has successfully recorded all meetings and poster sessions, making them publicly accessible through YouTube and various other channels. Additionally, we have given a radio talk aimed at enhancing public awareness of dark matter studies. Furthermore, above given scientific summary of the meeting will be published in a layman’s format, available in multiple languages to reach diverse audiences. We invite you to stay tuned for future updates on the [FM9 website](#).

Outreach Activities Conducted within FM9: We have also organised a ‘student engagement activity’, namely [SEA@UWC](#), bringing together a distinguished panel of international experts (Prof. Matthew Colless, Dr. Caroline Foster, Dr. Sadona Price, Dr. Michale Hilker, and Dr. Gauri Sharma,) who sat among the students to encourage open dialogue and discussions. This activity was hosted at Physics and Astronomy Department of University of the Western Cape, attracting about 50 enthusiastic undergraduate and postgraduate students. The main topic of discussion was: (1) science ideas and funding schemes, (2) putting knowledge into action, (3) critical reasoning skills, (4) constructive communication and collaboration, (5) data/information management, and (6) stress and fear management. *This event not only provided a platform for learning and self-reflection but also strengthened the sense of community among students and faculty. By addressing these critical topics, we continues to demonstrate our commitment to the holistic development of our next-generation, equipping them with the tools needed to thrive both academically and personally.* Lastly, as a part of FM9, we also participated in the school outreach conducted by GA2024. Images are added in the Gallery section, and [SEA@UWC](#) event is highlighted [here](#).

Country and Gender Plot:

SOC were chosen from all four major continents, with no more than 30% from any one specific country. The final selection of invited and contributed talks was conducted through an internal voting process. Each contributed abstract was ranked by the Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) members using the GA24-organized Oxford system. Each step of the meeting, including scientific program, was designed to reflect a balance in professional levels, age, gender, and country representation. Special priority was given to young researchers and women in the field.

Executive Summary:

1. The FM9 was successfully conducted over two days (13th and 15th Aug 2024), featuring six thematic sessions: Observational Constraints on Dark Matter I & II, Λ CDM Challenges and Simulations, Constraining Dark Matter Particle Candidates, Alternatives to Λ CDM, and Perspectives and New Techniques.
2. The program included a total of 42 presentations, comprising six invited talks and 36 contributed talks. This included 14 flash talks, six online presentations, and 36 in-person presentations, alongside 78 e-posters.
3. The final selection of invited and contributed talks was conducted through an internal voting process. Each contributed abstract was ranked by the Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC) members using the GA24-organized Oxford system.
4. The scientific program was designed to reflect a balance in professional levels, age, gender, and country representation. Special priority was given to young researchers and women in the field.
5. In cases where the quality of research did not meet the criteria for a full talk, participants were provided the opportunity to present an e-poster.
6. In total FM9 received 13,475 euros IAU grant and 8098 euros South African grant, which supported 23 and 11 participants, respectively, for travel and registration fee.
7. All participants were encouraged to prepare proceedings for their talks and posters (e.g., see General assembly Proceedings Focus Meeting 9).
8. In line with the FM9 proposal's commitment to public contribution, chairs have actively conducted and participated in student engagement initiatives and public outreach programs.

Gallery:

School Outreach: 5th Aug 2024

School Outreach: 5th Aug 2024

[SEA@UWC](#) Event: 14th Aug 2024

[SEA@UWC](#) Event: 14th Aug 202

Focus Meeting 9: 13th Aug 2024

probably, my phone switched to lowest, possible, resolution :(

Focus Meeting 9: 15th Aug 2024

We thank IAU GA2024 for providing this wonderful platform to discuss the unknowns of the Universe!